

Research Letter to Editor

Development and testing of the Outcome Prioritization Tool adjusted to older patients with cancer: A pilot study

Petronella A.L. Seghers^a, Marije E. Hamaker^a, Hanneke van der Wal-Huisman^b,
 Mariken E. Stegmann^c, Johanneke E.A. Portielje^d, Pauline de Graeff^e, Suzanne Festen^{e,*}

^a Department of Geriatric Medicine, Diaconessenhuis, 3582 KE Utrecht, the Netherlands

^b Department of Surgery, University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, 9700 RB Groningen, the Netherlands

^c University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, Department of General Practice and Elderly Care Medicine, 9700 RB Groningen, the Netherlands

^d Department of Medical Oncology, Leiden University Medical Center-LUMC, 2333 ZA Leiden, the Netherlands

^e University of Groningen, University Medical Center Groningen, University Center for Geriatric Medicine, 9700 RB Groningen, the Netherlands

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Health outcome priorities
 Patient priorities
 Shared decision making
 Geriatric oncology

1. Introduction

In older patients with cancer, the balance between harms and benefits of treatment is delicate. There is a higher risk of adverse outcomes of cancer treatment due to comorbidity and geriatric impairments, while clinical benefit is uncertain due to their frequent exclusion in clinical trials [1,2]. Potential benefits of treatment (for example, increased survival) may come at a cost (for example, increased treatment side-effects or loss of function). As a result, treatment decisions are often preference sensitive, which means that the optimal treatment choice depends on a patient's personal values and priorities [3].

These values and priorities need to be explicitly discussed. There is no single outcome that all (older) patients give highest priority to and physicians are often unable to correctly estimate what matters most to their patients [4–6]. Currently, less than half of the patients with cancer perceive that their values and priorities are discussed [4,5,7]. Knowing what is important for the patient aids the healthcare professional in tailoring treatment to the patient's values and priorities, which may prevent decision regret. This conversation may be facilitated by using a conversation tool. Various methods exist to elicit patient priorities for health outcomes, mostly developed for research [8]. A method that is widely studied, and that is already used in clinical practice, is the Outcome Prioritization Tool (OPT) [9]. The OPT is a conversation tool that uses four universal health outcomes and is neither disease nor

treatment specific, which makes it suitable for older patients with multiple diseases [10] (details in Webappendix A). However, the OPT does not contain all the priorities that a recent systematic review found to be important to patients with cancer [6]. In particular, the impact of treatments is not included. Therefore, we chose to adapt the OPT to older patients with cancer (OPT–C). This paper describes the development and testing of this tool.

2. Methods

This is a prospective study to develop the OPT-C and to pilot it. It was a collaborative effort between the University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG) and Diaconessenhuis Utrecht, the Netherlands. The study received a waiver for full ethics review from the institutional review board and was approved by the local research committee. All results were reported using descriptive data.

More information about the original OPT including the rationale as to why the OPT was chosen as tool to be used can be found in Webappendix A. Webappendix B describes our adaptation process. In short, outcomes important to patients with cancer were extracted from a recently performed systematic review [6]. This review included 28 studies and 4374 patients with cancer. Additional input was provided by the GERONTE panel, which includes experts with various backgrounds, all involved in the care of older patients with cancer ($n = 30$; <https://>

* Corresponding author at: Hanzeplein 1, 9700RB Groningen, The Netherlands.
 E-mail address: s.festen@umcg.nl (S. Festen).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgo.2023.101590>

Received 27 September 2022; Received in revised form 20 June 2023; Accepted 7 July 2023

Available online 21 July 2023

1879-4068/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

GERONTEproject.eu/). The selected health outcomes were approved during an online expert meeting. Subsequently, an adapted version of the original instructions developed by UMCG [9] was made with feedback from geriatricians and advanced practice nurses in oncology (Webappendix C).

In the second step, patients aged over 70 years, diagnosed with cancer or treated for cancer during the last two years, tested the OPT—C, either in relation to an actual treatment decision or to a hypothetical situation in which they had to make a new treatment decision. The proportion of patients that were able to complete the OPT-C in accordance with instructions was measured to look at feasibility. Patients were also asked how difficult they found the use of the OPT-C by filling out a visual analogue scale from 0 to 100 (easy-difficult). Additionally, patients were asked whether they thought the OPT-C would be helpful in their consultation with their physician.

The healthcare professionals were invited to fill out a survey each time they had used the OPT-C with a patient to share their experiences. After using the OPT-C for three to five times, the healthcare professionals were asked to compare the OPT-C with the OPT. Webappendix D describes step 1 and 2 in more detail.

3. Results

3.1. Step 1: Development of the OPT-C and Instructions

Both the expert panel and the systematic review which provided the patient’s perspective prioritized the outcomes survival and maintaining independence, but the importance of avoiding or preventing negative treatment effects was also highlighted (Webappendix E). This item was therefore selected for inclusion in the OPT-C tool.

Additionally, scoping literature research on the development of conversation aids and prioritization tools revealed that patients became overwhelmed if they were asked to trade off more than four health outcomes [10]. Therefore, in order to allow for the inclusion of the additional health outcome, the two outcomes relating to symptoms (‘reducing pain’ and ‘reducing other symptoms’) were combined into one (‘reducing pain and other symptoms’; Table 1). ‘Extending life’ and ‘maintaining independence’ were kept without any alterations. To finalize the new tool, the three primary researchers (NS, SF, MH) discussed how best to phrase the newly added item so that it would cover a broad range of negative treatment effects. In the end, we felt that ‘preventing negative treatment effects’ was the most fit for this purpose.

3.2. Step 2a: Pilot of the OPT-C in Patients

The OPT-C was used in 19 patients in a hypothetical treatment decision and in six patients during an actual treatment decision. They were included between February 2022 and May 2022. The median age was 78 years (range 71–93) and 48% were male (Webappendix E&F). Most patients were treated for lymphoma (various types; $n = 6$; 24%; Webappendix E&F).

The OPT-C was used in accordance to instructions in 84% ($n = 21$; Fig. 1a). Patients rated the difficulty of using the OPT score a median of 30/100 (with 0 being easy and 100 being difficult), with an interquartile

Table 1
Health outcomes of original OPT vs OPT—C.

Original OPT	OPT-C
1. Extending life	1. Extending life
2. Maintaining independence	2. Maintaining independence
3. Reducing pain	3. Reducing pain and other bsymptoms
4. Reducing other symptoms	4. Preventing negative treatment effects

Table to illustrate the included health outcomes of the OPT and OPT—C. OPT; Outcome Prioritization Tool, OPT—C; OPT adapted to older patients with cancer.

range of 0–60. The majority ($n = 16$; 64%) thought the OPT-C would be helpful during their conversations with their treating oncologists. Life extension and maintaining independence were most frequently prioritized as the most important goals (Webappendix E).

3.3. Step 2b: Pilot of the OPT-C in Healthcare Professionals

Seven healthcare professionals with a geriatric background were included to test the OPT—C. Of the seven, six had experience with the original OPT before they participated. In total the healthcare professionals had 19 OPT-C conversations. In 89% ($n = 17$) of the conversations, healthcare professionals mentioned that they were able to define patient priorities using the OPT—C. The healthcare professionals mentioned that the OPT-C was used by the patients in according with instructions in 79% ($n = 15$). Some healthcare professionals mentioned, that if it was not used in accordance with instructions, it would still provide value information. Healthcare professionals felt that the instructions were clear for 89% ($n = 17$) of the patients. They thought the OPT-C would contribute in the treatment decision in eight patients (42%; Fig. 1b). After trying the OPT-C three to five times, all healthcare professionals preferred the OPT-C to be used in older patients with cancer, but also mentioned that it depended on patient characteristics.

4. Discussion

In this pilot study we developed and tested an adjusted version of the OPT [9] for patients with cancer, the OPT—C. The OPT-C appears to be a feasible tool to aid the conversation on priorities of health outcomes in older patients with cancer. Most patients were able to use it in accordance with instructions and healthcare professionals were able to assess the patient priorities for health outcomes using the OPT—C. Furthermore, the majority of patients perceived that using the OPT-C would aid their conversation with their healthcare professional and a substantial part of the healthcare professionals thought the OPT-C would improve the decision-making process.

In previous studies, a similar percentage (9.1%- 30.6% compared to 21%in this study) of older patients with cancer were unable to use the OPT to prioritize their health outcomes [11]. The OPT-C showed similar feasibility to the original OPT. Some of the possible explanations for some patient’s inability to complete the OPT-C may be lower education level, poor health literacy, or cognitive decline. However, even when a patient was not able to prioritize their health outcomes, it was still possible to have a conversation about what matters to them with this tool.

Not all patients found the tool to be helpful, and not all healthcare professionals thought the OPT-C would contribute to the final treatment decision. For instance, when priorities are already clarified or when priorities are in line with treatment options, using a tool to discuss priorities may not contribute much to the final decision and, thus, may not be considered helpful. However, even in these cases it may be good to verify that treatment decisions are in line with the patient’s priorities. The OPT-C can aid in structurally discussing priorities. The OPT-C is relatively easy to implement and free to use, and, given the potential impact, we believe it is worth the extra effort.

We did not directly compare the OPT-C with the OPT, but asked healthcare professionals which they preferred. They felt that for certain patient groups, the OPT-C may provide a better balance between the health outcomes, for example, in the absence of pain. However, which tool is most suitable to use in the individual patient will depend on the situation. If lasting negative treatment effects may be a likely treatment outcome, such as patients receiving chemotherapy, the OPT-C might be preferred. The original OPT on the other hand, might be more suitable for patients having a high disease-related symptom burden. Regardless of the tool used, the exact health outcomes included in the conversation tool are probably less important than the information on values and priorities that is collected during the conversation. For this, both OPT

Fig. 1. a. Patients’ perspectives on OPT-C feasibility. Results from the patient pilot, after trying the OPT—C, patients were asked two additional questions as mentioned below. $N = 25$. b. Healthcare professionals’ perspectives on OPT-C feasibility. In total, 7 healthcare professionals answered the following questions each time after using the OPT—C. In total, they used it 19 times. OPT; Outcome Prioritization Tool, OPT—C; OPT adapted to older patients with cancer.

versions can be used, depending also on healthcare professionals’ experience with these tools.

This study has some limitations. In the development of the new OPT—C, we used input from a range of clinicians and used a systematic review which described patient’s outcome prioritization. Although the systematic review included data from 4374 patients, patients were not included in the final selection of the four outcomes. If patients were included they could have aided in the exact phrasing of the four outcomes, to verify that they represented their priorities well. Second, we did not have a predefined threshold for feasibility. While the information on the clinician’s and patient’s experience of using the instrument does provide insight in the feasibility of the tool, the lack of a clear threshold means that it is not possible to draw definitive conclusions.

Additionally, the results may have been impacted by the selected patient population. Although all patients with cancer were eligible, mainly patients that were receiving chemotherapy or other systemic therapies were included. It may be that patients who need to undergo surgery, or patients that have never experienced any oncologic treatments have other priorities or have more difficulty using the OPT—C. Some patients who had experience with oncologic treatments filled in the OPT-C in a hypothetical situation; other patients were inexperienced with oncologic treatments and filled out the OPT-C while making a real treatment decision. Although this may have impacted the results, it also allowed for testing in both experienced and inexperienced patients.

Only physicians with a geriatric background tested the OPT—C. Future research is needed to test the OPT-C with other healthcare professionals, such as oncologists, advanced practice nurses, general practitioners, or surgeons. Another focus of future research is to test validity and reliability in a larger group and in different patient categories, for example, those with cognitive impairment. Additionally, future studies could investigate the effect the OPT-C has on treatment decisions and patient outcomes. An example of a future large randomized clinical trial

that will use the OPT-C is GERONTE [12].

In conclusion, in this pilot study the OPT-C appears to be a feasible instrument to discuss values and priorities with older patients with cancer. It helps to initiate a conversation and aids the patient in expressing what health outcomes are most important to them, thereby giving them a more active role in shared decision-making. Future research should focus on testing the OPT-C in larger and different patient groups, testing it with different healthcare professionals, and evaluating the effect of the OPT-C on treatment decisions and, consequently, on outcomes like quality of life and treatment satisfaction.

Declarations of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Author Contributions

- Conception and Design: MH, SF.
- Data Collection: NS, MH, SF.
- Analysis and Interpretation of Data: NS, SF, MH.
- Manuscript Writing: All.
- Approval of Final Article: All.

Funding

This research was funded by GERONTE. The GERONTE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 945218.

Appendix A. Supplementary Data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgo.2023.101590>.

References

- [1] Hurria A, Togawa K, Mohile SG, Owusu C, Klepin HD, Gross CP, et al. Predicting chemotherapy toxicity in older adults with cancer: a prospective multicenter study. *J Clin Oncol* 2011;29(25):3457–65. <https://doi.org/10.1200/JCO.2011.34.7625>.
- [2] DuMontier C, Loh KP, Soto-Perez-de-Celis E, Dale W. Decision making in older adults with Cancer. *J Clin Oncol* 2021;39(19):2164–74. <https://doi.org/10.1200/jco.21.00165>.
- [3] O'Connor AM, Légaré F, Stacey D. Risk communication in practice: the contribution of decision aids. *Br Med J* 2003;327(7417):736–40. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.327.7417.736>.
- [4] Mulley A, Trimble C, Elwyn G. Stop the silent misdiagnosis: patients' preferences matter. *Med J Aust* 2012;345(7883):23–6.
- [5] Festen S, Stegmann ME, Prins A, van Munster BC, van Leeuwen BL, Halmos GB, et al. How well do healthcare professionals know of the priorities of their older patients regarding treatment outcomes? *Patient Educ Couns* 2021;104(9):2358–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2021.02.044>.
- [6] Seghers PAL Nelleke, Wiersma A, Festen S, Stegmann ME, Soubeyran P, Rostoft S, et al. Patient preferences for treatment outcomes in oncology with a focus on the older patient; a systematic review. *Cancers (Basel)* 2022;14(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/cancers14051147>.
- [7] Kuijpers MMT, Veenendaal H, Engelen V, Visserman E, Noteboom EA, Stiggelbout AM, et al. Shared decision making in cancer treatment: a dutch national survey on patients' preferences and perceptions. *Eur J Cancer Care (Engl)* 2021:e13534. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecc.13534>.
- [8] Hazlewood GS. Measuring patient preferences: an overview of methods with a focus on discrete choice experiments. *Rheum Dis Clin N Am* 2018;44(2):337–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rdc.2018.01.009>.
- [9] Stegmann ME, Festen S, Brandenburg D, Schuling J, van Leeuwen B, de Graeff P, et al. Using the outcome prioritization tool (OPT) to assess the preferences of older patients in clinical decision-making: a review. *Maturitas* 2019;128:49–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2019.07.022>.
- [10] Fried TR, Tinetti M, Agostini J, Iannone L, Towle V. Health outcome prioritization to elicit preferences of older persons with multiple health conditions. *Patient Educ Couns* 2011;83(2):278–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2010.04.032>.
- [11] Festen S, Kok M, Hopstaken JS, van der Wal-Huisman H, van der Leest A, Reyners AKL, et al. How to incorporate geriatric assessment in clinical decision-making for older patients with cancer. An implementation study. *J Geriatr Oncol* 2019;10(6):951–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgo.2019.04.006>.
- [12] Streamlined. Geriatric and Oncological evaluation based on IC Technology (GERONTE) for holistic patient-oriented healthcare management for older multimorbid patients. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 945218, <https://geronteproject.eu/> (accessed 2022-06-24).